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Enhancing Preparedness for Landfill Disasters Through Virtual Reality Simulations

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THE PROBLEM

Population Increases

We are currently around 8.1 billion people.

Solid Waste Increases

Solid waste increases with population and economic growth

Estimating solid waste by using population and GDP growth

As populations grow and economies expand, waste generation per capita increases. As a result, the escalating volume of waste necessitates efficient waste management solutions.

Landfills are the most common way to dispose of waste

70% of the world's waste ends up in landfills, which are the most basic type of Solid Waste Disposal System (SWDS)

LANDFILLS HAVE PROBLEMS TOO

GREENHOUSE GAS

As organic mass in landfills decompose, methane gas is released. Methane absorbs the sun's heat more than CO₂, making it a more potent greenhouse gas.

WATER CONTAMINATION

Leachate from landfills can contaminate ground and surface water, threatening aquatic ecosystems and drinking water supplies.

SURFACE/SUBSURFACE FIRES

Surface and subsurface fires at landfills are common and difficult to control, releasing toxic smoke that endangers nearby communities.

EFFECT ON THE ECOSYSTEM

Creation of landfills destroy natural habitats for wildlife.

PUBLIC HEALTH RISK

Health effects of living close to landfills can result to breathing disorders, cancers, and birth defects.

RUNNING OUT OF ROOM

PEAK WASTE PRODUCTION

Peak waste production is expected to occur within this century, with estimates suggesting that by 2050, waste production will reach 3542 Mt

MISMANAGEMENT

As the volume of waste increase waste management becomes more challenging and could result in catastrophic events

PROPOSED SOLUTION

IMMERSION

Stimulate the senses to invoke the feeling of presence.

INTERACTION

The ability to manipulate an object in an environment

NAVIGATION

The ability to move in space in a given direction

VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

A synthetic space with a given set of rules governing everything within it.

WHAT IS VR?

WHY?

COST EFFECTIVE

VR provides a scalable solution that can be easily updated and distributed, making it a cost-effective and flexible training tool

CONFIDENCE

VR education helps to reduce anxiety in users, which is crucial for handling real-life emergencies

RETENTION

VR materials can motivate trainees to use acquired knowledge and skills in practice

RISK-FREE

The VR training will enable them to practice response strategies, decision-making, and problem-solving in a risk-free setting.

LANDFILL RESCUE SIMULATION

INTERACTION

Interactable environment. Users are able to make risk-free decisions.

EDUCATION

Showcases historical catastrophes that have led to regulations and reforms of landfills.

TRAINING

Discusses the appropriate steps to mitigate potentially disastrous events

IMPACT

Simulates the impacts of landfills on public health, environment, and wildlife.

HISTORICAL LANDFILL SIMULATION

HISTORICAL RECREATIONS

A 23-acre Superfund site in Kentucky, became notorious for severe contamination due to illegal dumping of waste drums.

Valley of the Drums

Was the world's largest landfill until its closure in 2001. The site consisted of four mounds ranging from 90 to 225 feet in height

Fresh Kills Landfill

Love Canal

A 16-acre tract in New York, was a chemical waste dumpsite for Hooker Chemical Corporation between 1942 and 1953.

Bridgeton Landfill

An active 200-acre Superfund site in Bridgeton, Missouri, faced radiological contamination in 1973 due to illegal dumping.

TECHNOLOGY

VR DEVELOPMENT PIPELINE

3D MODELING

Rendering 3D models to represent real-world objects

TEXTURING

Adding texture and paint onto 3D objects

GAME ENGINE

Importing all finished models into a game engine to bring to life

PROJECTION

The final simulation is projected onto a VR platform, such as a headset

CURRENT PROGRESS

Model Development and Integration

Models have been successfully built and integrated into the VR simulations using Autodesk Maya and Unity.

Simulation of Landfill Piles

A procedural generator was developed to create multiple instances of various types of debris, adding diversity and authenticity to the virtual landfill scenes

Interactive Elements

Physics were applied to objects, making them interactable and responsive to user actions.

Natural Elements

The VR simulations also include natural elements such as trees and foliage. These elements were placed within the environment, and wind effects were added to create a dynamic and immersive experience.

Environmental Effects

A heat map view of subsurface fires has been implemented to visualize underground fire activity. Additionally, realistic effects such as water, rain, and fire have been recreated to simulate environmental scenarios that users may encounter.

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